

Digital media and disinformation: a comparative study on lifestyle, sports and health among young students from Ourinhos/SP and Botucatu/SP

CUBAS-SILVA, J.A.¹ ; SANCHES,M.D.² ; PENATTI,D.A.² ; AMERICO,M.¹

¹The Doctoral (PhD) in Media and Technology Post-graduation Program - PPGMiT in the School of Architecture, Arts, Communication and Design - São Paulo State University (UNESP) – Bauru, SP, Brazil.

²Botucatu Medical School, São Paulo State University (UNESP), Botucatu, SP, Brazil.

Introduction: Digital technologies occupy a growing space in society, exposing children and adolescents to a wide range of often unreliable information. This exposure to diverse content and disinformation in digital media directly impacts the lifestyle and health of young people in contemporary times. **Objective:** The main objective of this study is to identify the habits and perceptions of young students in relation to healthy living and to analyze the influence of misinformation on their daily lives. Based on these findings, the work aims to promote educational and awareness-raising actions to mitigate the effects of excessive screen use and encourage healthy eating and physical activity practices. **Materials and Methods:** This is a comparative study with a qualitative and quantitative approach, involving students from public schools in Ourinhos/SP and Botucatu/SP. The survey in Ourinhos/SP was carried out in two stages: (1) physical evaluation and health habits of students entering the 1st year of high school in 2022; and (2) application of a questionnaire in 2024, with the same students (then in the 3rd year), addressing media consumption, misinformation, eating habits and sports practice. The second survey will be conducted in Botucatu/SP, with the application of questionnaires and educational interventions (lectures, dynamics and conversation circles). A new application of the questionnaire after the interventions will allow the comparative analysis of the data and the evaluation of the impact of the actions. Results: Preliminary data obtained in Ourinhos/SP indicate a worrying contradiction: although 68.3% of students report practicing physical activity, there is a significant incidence in the use of medications, including psychotropics, and the maintenance of unhealthy habits, suggesting the influence of the media. In addition, 65.7% of young people said they knew someone of the same age group who had already followed diets published on the internet. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The partial results highlight the importance of school as a crucial environment for health promotion and media literacy development. The study is in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda, in particular SDG 3 (Health and Wellbeing) and SDG 4 (Quality Education). The research concludes that educational strategies that consider the digital environment in which young people are inserted are necessary, aiming to form a more critical, healthy and conscious youth in the face of complex media content.

Keywords: Misinformation. Educational strategies. Healthy habits.